

THE IMPORTANCE OF ASSESSING STUDENT LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12634302>

Annotation: This article gives information about assessment refers to the deliberate gathering of evidence of student learning to allow both teachers and learners to measure progress in a course. Therefore, assessments provide us with an opportunity to improve student learning, as well as to enhance our teaching through critical reflection on the results of the assessments.

Key words: assessment, formative, summative,

Student assessment is, arguably, the centerpiece of the teaching and learning process and therefore the subject of much discussion in the scholarship of teaching and learning. Without some method of obtaining and analyzing evidence of student learning, we can never know whether our teaching is making a difference. That is, teaching requires some process through which we can come to know whether students are developing the desired knowledge and skills, and therefore whether our instruction is effective. Learning assessment is like a magnifying glass we hold up to students' learning to discern whether the teaching and learning process is functioning well or is in need of change. The scholarship of teaching and learning discusses two general forms of assessment. The first, summative assessment, is one that is implemented at the end of the course of study, for example via comprehensive final exams or papers. Its primary purpose is to produce an evaluation that "sums up" student learning. Summative assessment is comprehensive in nature and is fundamentally concerned with learning outcomes. While summative assessment is often useful for communicating final evaluations of student achievement, it does so without providing opportunities for students to reflect on their progress, alter their learning, and demonstrate growth or improvement; nor does it allow instructors to modify their teaching strategies before student learning in a course has concluded.

The second form, formative assessment, involves the evaluation of student learning at intermediate points before any summative form. Its fundamental purpose is to help students *during* the learning process by enabling them to reflect on their challenges and growth so they may improve. By analyzing students' performance through formative assessment and sharing the results with them, instructors help students to "understand their strengths and

weaknesses and to reflect on how they need to improve over the course of their remaining studies”. Pat Hutchings refers to as “assessment behind outcomes”: “the promise of assessment—mandated or otherwise—is improved student learning, and improvement requires attention not only to final results but also to *how* results occur. Assessment *behind outcomes* means looking more carefully at the process and conditions that lead to the learning we care about...”. Formative assessment includes all manner of coursework with feedback, discussions between instructors and students, and end-of-unit examinations that provide an opportunity for students to identify important areas for necessary growth and development for themselves.

It is important to recognize that both summative and formative assessment indicate the *purpose* of assessment, not the *method*. Different methods of assessment can either be summative or formative depending on when and how the instructor implements them. Sally Brown and Peter Knight in *Assessing Learners in Higher Education* caution against a conflation of the method (e.g., an essay) with the goal (formative or summative): “Often the mistake is made of assuming that it is the method which is summative or formative, and not the purpose. This, we suggest, is a serious mistake because it turns the assessor’s attention away from the crucial issue of feedback”. If an instructor believes that a particular method is formative, but he or she does not take the requisite time or effort to provide extensive feedback to students, the assessment effectively functions as a summative assessment despite the instructor’s intentions (Brown and Knight, 1994). Indeed, feedback and discussion are critical factors that distinguish between formative and summative assessment; formative assessment is only as good as the feedback that accompanies it.

There are several steps in this planning process.

1. Defining learning goals. An assessment plan usually begins with a clearly articulated set of learning goals.
2. Defining assessment methods. Once goals are clear, an instructor must decide on what evidence – assignment(s) – will best reveal whether students are meeting the goals. We discuss several common methods below, but these need not be limited by anything but the learning goals and the teaching context.
3. Developing the assessment. The next step would be to formulate clear formats, prompts, and performance criteria that ensure students can prepare effectively and provide valid, reliable evidence of their learning.
4. Integrating assessment with other course elements. Then the remainder of the course design process can be completed. In both integrated (Fink 2013) and

backward course design models (Wiggins & McTighe 2005), the primary assessment methods, once chosen, become the basis for other smaller reading and skill-building assignments as well as daily learning experiences such as lectures, discussions, and other activities that will prepare students for their best effort in the assessments.

5. Communicate about the assessment. Once the course has begun, it is possible and necessary to communicate the assignment and its performance criteria to students. This communication may take many and preferably multiple forms to ensure student clarity and preparation, including assignment overviews in the syllabus, handouts with prompts and assessment criteria, rubrics with learning goals, model assignments (e.g., papers), in-class discussions, and collaborative decision-making about prompts or criteria, among others.

6. Administer the assessment. Instructors then can implement the assessment at the appropriate time, collecting evidence of student learning – e.g., receiving papers or administering tests.

7. Analyze the results. Analysis of the results can take various forms – from reading essays to computer-assisted test scoring – but always involves comparing student work to the performance criteria and the relevant scholarly research from the field(s).

Used literatures:

1. Kurbanovna, A. N. (2024). ISSUES OF LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AT A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION. Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 11(06), 269-270.
2. Aliqulova, M. (2024). АНАЛИЗ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ АИ КУПРИНА. О ‘ЗБЕК TILINING HORIJDА О ‘QITILISHI: TA’LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI, 1(01), 82-87.
3. Аликулова, М. Ш. (2023). ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАССКАЗОВ АЛЕКСАНДРА КУПРИНА. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(12 Part 2), 172-174.
4. Bazarova, D. (2024). TA’LIM RUS TILIDA OLIB BORILADIGAN GURUHLARDA “O ‘ZBEK TILIDA SO ‘Z TARKIBI” MAVZUSINI O ‘RGATISH TAJRIBASIDAN. O ‘ZBEK TILINING HORIJDА O ‘QITILISHI: TA’LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI, 1(01), 88-90.
5. Bazarova, D. B. (2023). ON THE USE OF ALTERNATIVE WORDS. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 3(05), 48-51.
6. Аликулова, М. М. (2023). ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ РОДА FERULA КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ И ИХ ЗАЩИТА ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВОМ

РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Биология и интегративная медицина, (4 (63)), 196-202.

7. Манноновна, А. М. (2022). Лекарственное Поражение Печени И Применение Гепатопротекторов При Этой Патологии. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(4), 294-300.

8. Джалолов, Ф. Ф. (2021). Причины низкого усвоения знаний в общеобразовательных средних школах. Среднеевропейский научный вестник», журнал импакт-фактора, 11.

9. ISSN, R. S. A. 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 3, Mar., 2022 Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. ISSN, Rustamova Shahnoza Aripovna, 2776-0979.

10. Rustamova, S. A., & Shaxzoda, S. (2023). THE VALUE OF COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS FORMING CULTURE HISTORICAL BASES. " GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).

11. Sh, B. P. (2021). Ideas of Mahmudhoja Behbudi Reflected in Publicism. JournalNX, 7(10), 112-115.

12. Tagayeva, T., & Amanova, S. (2024, April). STYLISTIC PECULIARITIES OF LITERARY TEXT IN CREATIVE WORKS OF BERNARD SHAW. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 520-524).

13. Tagayeva, T., & Kabridinova, K. (2024, April). INDIVIDUAL FEATURES OF ARTISTIC STYLE OF WM THACKERAY. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 543-546).

14. Abdullayeva, N. K., & Bakhshilloyeva, N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 2(6), 19-28.

15. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O 'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. Interpretation and researches, (4 (26)).

16. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.

17. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So 'Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. Scholar, 1(13), 22-27.

18. Shodieva, G. (2023). TRANSPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(4), 40-46.

19. Yusupova, S. A. Z., & kizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(1), 300-304.
20. Tursunova, M., & Qizi, S. G. N. (2023). NAVIGATING ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN BUSINESS DISCOURSE: AN EXPLORATION OF DISCOURSE ETHICS. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 5), 687-690

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